

UDC 614.2:331.105.44(477.83/.86)“18/19”(091)

<https://doi.org/10.26641/2307-0404.2021.3.242319>

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EVOLUTION OF THE HEALTH-RELATED ACTIVITY OF THE TRADE UNIONS OF GALICIA IN THE XIX - EARLY XX CENTURIES

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Цитування: Медичні перспективи. 2021. Т. 26, № 3. С. 197-204

Cited: Medicni perspektivi. 2021;26(3):197-204

Key words: *medicine, trade union, society, physicians, protection*

Ключові слова: *медицина, профспілка, суспільство, лікарі, захист*

Ключевые слова: *медицина, профсоюз, общество, врачи, защита*

Abstract. Evolution of the health-related activity of the trade unions of Galicia in the XIX - early XX centuries.

Berest I.R., Berest R.Ya., Pasichnyk M.S., Pasichnyk S.M., Savchuk H.M., Strelbytska S.M. *Based on the principle of historicism, systematic analysis, scientific and objective approach, the article analyzes the evolution and shows the activities of the Galician trade unions in health-related activity. The current state and development of historiography of the issue is shown, the history of the medical and trade union movement is studied, it is proved that common problems for all segments of the population became the main event among the trade unions of the XIX early - XX centuries. These issues provide significant material for the scientific study of other key issues of the complex history of Galicia in the Austro-Hungarian period, in particular: the organization of health care, medical education, governance, economic and social development, the rise of the Ukrainian national movement and the like. In the conditions of building democratic institutions of independent Ukraine, the analysis and accumulation of historical experience have not only scientific, but also cognitive, ideological-political and especially applied, practical significance. Almost any professional organization has tried to protect its members in some way. In early 1867, doctors in Lviv recognized the need to create their own professional association to organize social protection, to create a fund to support sick, infirm and impoverished colleagues, as well as their widows and orphans. Thus, it was decided to establish a separate Medical Society. In accordance with the provisions of the statute, the purpose of the Society of Galician Physicians was to work together on the development of medicine, primarily in the direction of its practical application, taking into account the relations of the population as a whole; promoting a spirit of cohesion and friendship between health professionals to jointly oversee medical affairs; providing material assistance to impoverished colleagues, families of deceased colleagues. Similar tasks were set by the societies of printers, weavers, and oil refiners. All of them were united by the medical and health-improving activity.*

Реферат. Эволюция лечебно-оздоровительного направления деятельности профсоюзов Галичины XIX – начала XX в. Берест И.Р., Берест Р.Я., Пасечник М.С., Пасечник С.М., Савчук Г.М., Стрельбицкая С.Н.

На основе принципа историзма, системного анализа, научного и объективного подхода в статье проанализирована эволюция и показана деятельность галицких профсоюзов лечебно-оздоровительного направления. Показано современное состояние и развитие историографии проблематики, исследована история медицинского и профсоюзного движения, доказано, что главным вопросом в среде профсоюзов XIX – начала XX в. стали общие проблемы для всех слоев населения. Указанная проблематика дает богатый материал для научной обработки других ключевых проблем комплексной истории Галичины австро-венгерского периода, в частности: организации системы здравоохранения, медицинского образования, системы управления в крае, экономического и социального развития, подъема украинского национального движения и тому подобное. В условиях развития демократических институтов независимой Украины анализ и аккумуляция исторического опыта имеют не только научное, но и познавательное, идейно-политическое и особенно прикладное, практическое значение. Практически любая профессиональная организация пыталась определенным образом защитить своих участников. В начале 1867 г. врачи Львова признали необходимость создания собственного профессионального объединения с целью организации социальной защиты, создания фонда для поддержки больных, немощных и обедневших коллег, также вдов и сирот по ним. Таким образом, было решено основать отдельное врачебное Общество. В соответствии с положениями устава, целью Общества галицких врачей

была совместная работа вокруг развития медицины, прежде всего в направлении ее практического применения, с учетом взаимоотношений населения государства в целом; пропаганда духа сплоченности и дружеских отношений между медицинскими работниками, чтобы совместно следить за делами в медицине; оказание материальной помощи обедневшим коллегам, семьям умерших коллег. Похожие задачи перед собой ставили и общества печатников, ткачей, нефтеперерабатывающего промысла. Их всех объединяло лечебно-оздоровительное направление деятельности.

In modern conditions, when researchers determine the ways of further development of Ukraine and medical science in particular, the growth of scientific interest in own history, rethinking of historical facts, ideological distortions, hidden events and phenomena is obvious. We are always interested in: how did it all start? What preceded this or that event? It is clear that medical science appeared a long time ago, but the organizations that aimed to protect medical workers are a new topic.

Therefore, the activities of the first proto-professional organizations in the Ukrainian lands, the problems of their medical care, the study of their cultural, educational, health and other needs were no exception. Such societies have become prototypes of modern trade unions.

Analysis of the national literature on the study of the history of medicine and its trade unions shows the need for a new comprehensive study in terms of our modern state-building, associated, first, with a small number of elucidated sources. Secondly, this topic is diverse and multifaceted, and many aspects of it need a deeper and more thorough review. The study of the historical development of the trade union movement leads to the conclusion that the main trends in the evolution of medical and health activities of trade unions in Eastern Galicia was academic development and the desire to protect their members.

The scientific novelty of the research lies in the attempt to comprehensively cover the process of emergence, development of medical and health activities of trade unions of the XIX – early XX centuries. based on the generalization of available literature and sources. The obtained result forms a qualitatively new scientific and cognitive view on the importance of medicine in the socio-political life of Galician society.

In the Ukrainian scientific literature there is no information about the activities of professional societies in Galicia in the field of health, although there is information about the study of societies and organizations in other fields [2, 3, 4, 6, 7, 16]. Therefore, the study is based on Polish historiography, in particular the works of A. Bober [17], W. Naidus [23], J. Grek, W. Zimbitsky [21]. Our research was based on such sources as archival

materials, the society's statute, dated 1874, general reports on the establishment of organizations, financial documents (annual reports) and the press of that time.

The main purpose of the publication – based on an objective, comprehensive analysis of available sources to show the process of change in the health care system of the Austro-Hungarian Empire from the emergence of health insurance funds to the building of resorts in the second half of the XIX - early XX century, as well as to draw parallels with the development of modern health care.

MATERIALS AND METHODS OF RESEARCH

To solve the tasks, we used a number of methods, including historical and medical. Thanks to this, it was possible to recreate events and facts in time, which allowed to recreate the process of development of the Society of Galician Physicians, the Society of Galician Printers, Catholic Societies, their history with all its peculiarities. The systematic approach provided research on the interaction of the medical trade union, civil society and other societies as subsystems of the general social system. The bibliosemantic method made it possible to determine the state of study of this problem and ways to solve it through the analysis of the statute, annual reports and reports of the company's management. In general, the methodological basis of the work is the principles of historicism, systematic, structural analysis, objectivity, comprehensiveness and consistency in the consideration of the chosen topic.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The trade union movement originated among printers in the first quarter of the twentieth century. It is worth mentioning the fact that, we are convinced, indicates the socialization of the worldview of employers. Everyone knows that injuries are quite difficult to avoid in any workplace and first aid is needed as soon as possible. Thus, on April 1, 1819, the pharmacy "Under the Roman Emperor Titus" began operating on the ground floor of a townhouse at Lychakivska Street 3, in Lviv. Employees of the printing house having benefits used its services [5]. Later, in the early twentieth century. it was renamed the "Antoni Erbar Pharmacy", but only printers were served at a reduced rate [13].

At that time, many workers became members of the workers' mutual benefit fund that existed at the

state printing house in Lviv [8]. Due to the main idea of the chairman Jan Sulkowski, the activity of his mutual benefit fund not only provided for sickness benefits, but also provided the worker and his family with medical care and medicines, gave financial support to unemployed printers, etc. [23].

The city-wide Society of Printers of Lviv became the first trade union organization that aimed to provide treatment for its members. At the general meeting on July 13, 1862, a draft of a new statute was discussed, as a result of which a new item was introduced. It concerned the visits to sick and maimed employees of the union at their place of residence or treatment. Ensuring the fulfillment of this requirement was entrusted to the most responsible members of the society - August Skerl (Fig. 1) and Cyprian Gomesky [5].

Fig. 1. August Skerl – responsible from the society of printers of Lviv for attending the sick

An important decision was made at a meeting on August 28, 1864. It was decided that an unemployed member of the Society who paid contributions and fall ill within two months was entitled to treatment at a general hospital at the expense of the Society only, and in case of death, according to paragraph 43 of the Statute, his widow could also recon on financial assistance [17].

A significant problem of the trade union of printers was the lack of basic medical care at the enterprises, in addition, widespread occupational diseases, occupational injuries were the important issues that needed to be addressed, and therefore were raised at meetings. Thus, it was unanimously decided to invite a doctor to work, to purchase the necessary tools, medicines and arrange a medical office at the administration of the Fellowship. The chairman of the board on behalf of the company had to conclude an agreement with the doctor on the amount of payment, duration of work and working conditions. It was planned to organize and conduct a regular out-of-turn free medical examination of all members of the fellowship of printing enterprises of Lviv, as well as urgent house-calls in various unforeseen cases. Later, the company signed such an agreement with doctor Anton Berger, Lviv [18].

But not only printers were engaged in treatment and rehabilitation. On September 8, 1865, at the general congress, a new version of the statute of the Lviv "Fellowship of Mercy of even-Christian" was approved. The first paragraph of this document stated that the purpose of the society was to provide its members with medicines and treatment in case of illness [26].

At the beginning of 1867, Lviv doctors recognized the need to create their own professional association to organize social protection, to create a fund to support sick, weak and impoverished colleagues, as well as their widows and orphans. Thus, it was decided to establish a separate medical society. In accordance with the provisions of the statute, the purpose of the Society of Galician Physicians was to work together on the development of medicine, primarily in the direction of its practical application, taking into account mutual relations of the population as a whole; promoting a spirit of cohesion and friendship between health professionals to jointly oversee medical affairs; provide financial help to impoverished colleagues, families of deceased colleagues (widows and orphans) [1].

As of the end of 1868, the number of active members was 98, of whom 59 were from Lviv and 39 lived outside the city. To understand the sphere of influence, representation and activities of the Society, we present the names of the cities of the region from which the current members were: Buchach, Brody, Tarnów, Bochnia, Vienna, Zolochiv, Wadowice, Krakow, Dolyna, Lancut, Rava-Ruska, Stry, Liski, Ropchytsia, Rzeszow, Drohobych, Husiatyn, Yaroslav, Kamyanka, Terebovlia, Novy Sanch, Sambir, Chortkiv, Przemyśl, Sniatyn, Nisko, Bibrka, Turka. Some cities had several representatives [19].

From 1877 to 1900 the Lviv section of the Society of Galician Physicians was functioning, thanks to which it was possible to open the Medical

Department in 1894, and from 1897 the first clinics at the Medical University began functioning [21] (modern Chernihivska Street, 3).

Fig. 2. Emblem of Society of Galician Physicians

Another organization that performed medical and health mission was the Society for mutual provision of private employees [22]. The organization's social mission was to protect poor and infirm employees, the disabled, the wives and families of deceased members of the organization, to provide orphans with financial support and financial assistance, as well as assistance in their education and employment. It became the initiator and author of the introduction of medical and social insurance, the implementation of project of the state pension reform for various groups, mostly the poor [27]. At the same time, the rich social elite considered it a great honor to become its honorary member. Such a difficult social consensus was achieved only due to the coordinated policy of the management of the central department of the society, aimed at close cohesion of society [15].

The "Skala" Catholic Society of Craft Youth in Lviv also performed an important mission. The company managed to create a medical fund, which became a transitional link in its transformation into a trade union organization [25].

The purpose of creating this fund was the need to provide assistance to members of the society in case of illness, injury or maiming, i.e. when the employee became temporarily incapacitated. Financial help was also paid in case of incapacity for work that did not require inpatient treatment for a period not exceeding one month. Partial monetary compensation for treatment in Lviv hospitals was envisaged, but not more than for three or four months.

The medical fund also actively promoted the recovery and recreation of members of the society in rural areas. To do this, each member of the society was obliged to pay 5 centiles per week to the fund without any delays.

Every craftsman who paid a certain amount of contributions continuously for 16 weeks was entitled to financial assistance, organized rest and rehabilitation. But those who did not pay contributions for 6 consecutive weeks were forced to pay in addition to the usual contribution of 2 centiles weekly, a fine for each overdue week, because otherwise the right to financial assistance in case of illness was lost [5].

A similar policy regarding the care of the sick was followed by the Ukrainian fellowship of craftsmen “Zorya”, founded in Lviv in 1884 [14], where the annual expenditures were spent on treatment of members of the society. Free medical care for members of “Zorya” in different periods was provided by well-known doctors of the time – Sh. Selsky, P. Sushkevych, Ye. Ozarkevych [9, 10, 11].

The oil-producing industry did not lag behind, the driving force of which in the medical and health protection of workers' rights was the "Brotherly Funds". It is important that they not only took care of sick, injured members of the society, families of the deceased, but also demanded fair wages, facilitation and improvement of working conditions,

organization of safety measures from the administrations of extractive enterprises. On February 23, 1898, the board of the “Brotherly Fund” of the Galician Credit Bank presented a petition to the District Administration of the Drohobych Mining Administration about the need to build a hospital (Fig. 3) [12].

The professional union of Lviv printers "Vohnyshche" initiated the creation of branches of the society in many cities of Eastern Galicia. It not only defended the socio-economic interests of its members, stood up for appropriate working conditions, safety, health care, decent wages, but also provided financial assistance to widows, orphans, children with disabilities, retirees.

Fig. 3. Petition of the Board of the “Brotherly Fund” to Galician Credit Bank from February 23, 1898 to the District Administration of the Mining Administration in Drohobych on the need to build a hospital

The activities of the society "Vohnysche" had different directions. Of particular importance among them was the concern to restore the health of members of their trade union. A recreation and health complex called "House of Health" was built

at its own expense in the village of Mykulychyn in the Stanislaviv region (Fig. 4).

The grand opening of the health resort took place on May 15, 1910 [20].

Fig. 4. Recreation and health center of the trade union of Lviv printers in Mykulychyn, 1910

The Professional Society of Lviv Printers was an integral part of the All-Austrian trade union movement. It became an example for the creation and activity of many trade unions not only in Galicia, but also in the whole Austro-Hungarian Empire. Thus, on December 29, 1910, at a meeting of the Lviv City Council, a decision was made to allocate 20,000 rooms for the construction of a medical complex for the Lviv Society of Physicians [24].

CONCLUSIONS

1. On the basis of specific historical sources, the article provides a theoretical generalization and scientific solution to an important problem, which was to study the evolution of medical and health activities of trade unions in Galicia. During the XIX – early XX centuries the trade unions of Eastern Galicia have evolved from mutual aid funds to full-fledged professional organizations. The development of trade unions was conditioned by the

constant search for means and opportunities for existence, the establishment of practical activities aimed at protecting the members of society. The purpose of the creation and operation of most trade unions were primarily socio-economic and cultural-educational goals. However, there ones, aimed at the development of medical and health-improving direction for the purpose of their functioning.

2. Trade unions have gone from simple changes in the statutes of organizations to the construction of hospitals and health complexes. Medical and health-improving institutions of the Galician professional societies were an integral part of all-Austrian medical system, which became an example for the creation and operation of many institutions not only in Galicia but also in the whole Austro-Hungarian Empire. However, the First World War destroyed many plans and existing projects.

3. Another feature of the activities of Galician trade unions was the system of accumulation of savings in a special fund in case of illness or death. This can be seen in the work of the Fellowship of Private Servants and the Catholic Society of Craft Youth "Skala" in Lviv. Such a practice did not exist in the health care of the Austro-Hungarian monarchy at that time.

4. Drawing parallels with modernity, we can note that in the middle of the XIX century on the territory

of modern Ukraine, the principles of medical self-government have already been formed and the basis of health insurance has been laid. In today's reality, we only strive for such things in order to get real protection of our rights. Therefore, it makes sense to review the achievements of history and improve the experience already gained.

Conflict of interests. Authors declare no conflict of interests.

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The article was received
2020.10.06

